

A FORECAST-BASED SIZING OF RESIDENTIAL BATTERY STORAGE SYSTEMS CONSIDERING LOAD FLEXIBILITY

Goran Veljanovski^{a, *}, Pande Popovski^a, Katerina Bilbiloska^b, Petar Krstevski^b, Aleksandra Krkoleva Mateska^b and Metodija Atanasovski^a

^a Faculty of Technical Sciences Bitola, University St Kliment Ohridski – Bitola, Bitola, North Macedonia

^b Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technologies, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Skopje, North Macedonia

* Correspondence: goran.veljanovski@uklo.edu.mk

Abstract: The proliferation of residential rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems has been driven by the continuous cost reductions in PV technology, the recent energy crisis, and the intensified public awareness regarding global warming. The evolving conditions require careful evaluation of the economic feasibility of the installation and use of rooftop PV systems, due to the discrepancy between PV production and peak demand periods. One potential solution to increase the revenue derived from the rooftop PV systems is the integration of battery energy storage systems (BESS). Although there is a trend of cost reduction of BESS, the high capital expenditures still remain a constraining factor of BESS. In order for BESS to achieve economic feasibility, they need to be optimally sized and operated in the most efficient manner. To achieve optimal battery sizing, it is essential to take into account factors directly associated with BESS, which include future load demand, tariff structures and rooftop PV output. In this study, to effectively address uncertainties in future PV production, conformal prediction (CP) is implemented to forecast rooftop PV generation within confidence intervals, while Monte Carlo simulations are performed to generate random samples within those intervals to capture the stochastic nature of PV production. This approach enables the derivation of a probability distribution of potential BESS capacities. Additionally, by implementing load shifting to maximize self-consumption, the required optimal capacity of the BESS is reduced by over 44% compared to scenarios without load shifting, which significantly enhances the economic feasibility of the BESS.

Keywords: Battery energy storage systems, Conformal prediction, Monte Carlo simulation, Optimization, Load shifting

1. Introduction

Reduction in Renewable Energy Sources (RES) generation investment costs and supportive policies have led to a rapid increase in RES integration in power systems, which has caused changes in both supply and demand side [1]. On the supply side, the intermittent weather-dependent nature of wind and solar energy sources, introduces higher uncertainties, leading to fluctuating power generation. To ensure reliability and security of the contemporary power system, additional flexibility is required. On the demand side, self-consumption schemes and the emergence of prosumers have altered traditional demand patterns and introduced greater uncertainties in load forecasts [2]. At the same time, the increased electricity prices volatility, which has been observed during the past two years, has further encouraged investments in PV systems, including rooftop PV systems and has created the environment for the suppliers to develop new or adapt the existing tariffs to utilize the potential of both consumers and prosumers [3]. Related to these developments, the discrepancy between PV production, which peaks during daylight hours, and peak demand periods, typically occurring in the mornings and evenings has become higher [4].

These evolving conditions require careful evaluation of the economic feasibility of the installation and use of rooftop PV systems. Prosumers are thus exploring ways to enhance the economic viability of their installed rooftop PV systems [5]. One potential solution to increase the revenue from rooftop PV systems, and thereby encourage further investments in PV systems, is the integration of BESS. Despite the high capital costs associated with BESS, they can be economically viable if optimally sized and operated efficiently [6, 7]. An inaccurate sizing of BESS can transform the anticipated benefits into drawbacks, as the capital and maintenance costs of a BESS are closely tied to its size. If the BESS is oversized, it becomes economically unviable, while an undersized BESS fails to deliver the expected benefits [8]. Consequently, determining the optimal size of a BESS is a critical process that must be approached with adequate care and precision. In recent years, extensive research has focused on residential BESS to identify methods to enhance their economic feasibility.

Varieties of optimization approaches have been implemented to determine the optimal capacity of BESS, each aiming to achieve specific objectives and operational goals. The authors in [9] developed an optimization tool combining genetic algorithm (GA) and multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming (MOMILP) algorithms to determine the optimal capacity and operational schedules for residential BESSs. The optimization objective is to minimize electricity costs and battery degradation while optimizing sizing and operation. This approach is validated on real residential data from Ireland. In [10] the authors introduced a novel methodology for sizing residential BESS, leveraging multi-year simulations with a detailed degradation model. The optimization tool focuses on maximizing self-consumption and optimizing economic performance over the battery's lifetime. Mulleriyawage and Shen in [11] formulated a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) optimization problem with the objective of minimizing annual electricity costs for a specified BESS capacity, to determine the optimal sizing of residential BESS, comparing the operational optimization method introduced in the study with a baseline self-consumption maximization (SCM)

Nomenclature

a – specific controllable appliance	n_{tot} – cycle life of a battery
A – set of controllable appliances	N-HiTS – neural hierarchical interpolation for time series
BESS – battery energy storage systems	P_{b2g} – power flowing from battery to grid
$C_{b,cpx}$ – capital expenditures of a battery	P_{b2L} – power flowing from battery to load
$C_{b,h}$ – price at which electricity is bought from the grid	P_{exp} – power exported to the grid
$C_{s,h}$ – price at which electricity is sold to the grid	P_{g2b} – power flowing from grid to battery
CP – conformal prediction	P_{g2L} – power flowing from grid to load
DR – demand response	P_h – power generated by a rooftop PV system at time h
DSM – demand side management	P_{imp} – power imported from the grid
E_{cap} – battery capacity	P_{pv2b} – power flowing from PV to battery
E_h^c – battery charging energy at time h	P_{pv2L} – power flowing from PV to load
E_h^d – battery discharging energy at time h	PV – photovoltaic
GA – genetic algorithm	RES – renewable energy sources
H – time of use of a given appliance	s – time at which an appliance is turned on
$H_{allowed}$ – time interval during which a controllable appliance is permitted to be turned on	SoC – battery state of charge
L_a^{def} – predefined load profile of appliance a	ToU – time-of-use
$L_{a,h}^{con}$ – power of appliance a at time h	$x_{a,h}$ – logical operator
L_h^{ncon} – power of all non-controllable appliances	η_c – battery charging efficiency factor
n_c^d – number of full cycles of a battery in a day	η_d – battery discharging efficiency factor

approach. The optimal capacity of a BESS in [12] is determined using the genetic algorithm multi-period optimal power flow (GA-MPOPF) approach, aimed at maximizing the self-consumption of the prosumer. The authors also demonstrate that while larger BESS sizes improve self-consumption, the effectiveness diminishes beyond certain limit. A rule-based approach for BESS optimization, with the aim of minimizing the cost of electricity (COE), under four different tariffs is proposed in [13]. A particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm implemented in two stages—first to determine the daily operation strategy and second to optimize the rated capacity and power of the BESS—is used in [14] to determine the optimal capacity of BESS for an industrial consumer. The objective function of the optimization is maximization of net profit of BESSs.

A different approach to determining the optimal capacity of BESS is implemented in [15, 17], incorporating the participation of prosumers in demand side management (DSM) programs aimed at maximizing their self-consumption. Authors in [15] demonstrate that alterations in residential demand profiles directly affect BESS capacity. Furthermore, the authors in [16] show that implementing DSM can reduce BESS capacity requirements by more than 50%, compared to scenarios without DSM, thereby lowering initial BESS costs

and enhancing economic feasibility. In [17], a MILP-based model is initially implemented to reduce daily energy costs through demand response (DR), and afterwards the BESS capacity that has the highest net present value (NPV) is selected as the optimal capacity.

A common characteristic of the aforementioned studies is that the determination of the optimal capacity of BESS is based on historical data, without accounting for forecasts or the uncertainties associated with rooftop PV generation and load consumption. However, in [18], a convolutional neural network - long short-term memory (CNN-LSTM) is implemented for load forecasting over a 7-day planning horizon, followed by the application of reinforcement learning (RL) agents, to optimize residential energy management and achieve significant electricity bill savings. Enhancing the accuracy and confidence in rooftop PV forecasts can be achieved by applying CP methods to quantify uncertainty instead of relying solely on point forecasts for each time step. Regarding this approach, the authors in [19] demonstrated, in an electricity market context, that a CP-based framework offers more reliable information about the probability distribution of PV power, resulting in enhanced power predictions. Although BESS capacity is highly influenced by future PV generation and consumer load profiles, both of which are subject to uncertainties, CP has not yet been applied to assess these uncertainties for BESS sizing. This paper introduces a novel approach that builds upon the existing studies while providing additional value.

The contribution of this paper can be summarized as:

- A novel framework for residential BESS capacity optimization considering uncertainties associated with rooftop PV generation and consumer demand. As a result, a distribution of potential adequate BESS capacities is derived.
- Monte Carlo simulation method is applied to effectively address the uncertainties related to future values of rooftop PV generation.
- Synthetic load is created to address the uncertainties associated with the load diagram of the consumer and capture the stochasticity of appliance use patterns in households.
- To capture the DSM potential of prosumers load shifting and appliance use optimization is implemented to maximize self-consumption and reduce the required BESS capacity.
- In addition, this paper adopts a neural hierarchical interpolation for time series (N-HiTS) model for probabilistic forecasting of rooftop PV generation. It is effective for forecasting time series with seasonal and daily characteristics such as solar radiation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the mathematical models that govern the proposed framework for optimizing the residential BESS capacity. Section 3 describes the methodology for calculating the distribution of the potential BESS capacities. Section 4 discusses the results, while Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Methodology

For this paper, a grid-connected prosumer, shown on Fig. 1 is considered. The prosumer has a rooftop PV system, and its electrical load consists of uncontrollable and controllable appliances that can be scheduled according to a DSM algorithm. The optimal battery size is

based on minimized total annual costs, which are associated with the costs of electricity supply of the consumer and battery investment and operational costs.

Fig. 1 Schematic of a grid-connected prosumer with BESS

The novel methodology proposed in this paper is used to determine the optimal BESS capacity, from a set of discrete values, that minimizes the prosumer costs while accounting for uncertainties in PV generation and load demand. It simulates hourly rooftop PV generation and synthetic load consumption for 100 independent yearly scenarios, capturing yearly variations. For each year, the optimal BESS capacity is calculated using optimization techniques. These yearly capacities are aggregated into a distribution, and the highest observed capacity value within the distribution is selected as the final optimal capacity, ensuring robustness and adaptability to varying conditions throughout the BESS lifecycle.

In order to account for the uncertainties associated with PV production, which has a significant impact on the BESS capacity, a probabilistic forecasting method is adopted. The probabilistic forecast defines a prediction interval, which is a range of values that the forecasted variable can take with a given probability. Hence, a 95% prediction interval should contain a range of values that include the actual future value with probability of 95%. Probabilistic forecasting aims to generate the full forecast distribution, providing a range of possible future outcomes along with their associated probabilities. The N-HiTS model for probabilistic forecasting, adopted in this paper, is effective for forecasting time series with seasonal and daily characteristics, such as solar radiation [19]. In addition, transfer learning is introduced to bypass poor forecasting results due to the limited set of radiation data of the location of a specific resident. Transfer learning refers to the process of pre-training a flexible model on a large dataset and using it later on other data with little to no training [20]. For pre-training the N-HiTS model, historical data for solar radiation, from rooftop PV plant and ground mounted PV plant located in different parts of North Macedonia, was obtained from [21]. Fig. 2 depicts the PV power potential on different parts of North Macedonia, showing that it does not vary significantly throughout the country.

Fig. 2 Photovoltaic power potential of North Macedonia [21]

To further increase the accuracy of the forecast and narrow the confidence intervals, multiple forecasts with probabilities of occurrence are obtained instead of relying on a single forecast for each day. To achieve this, the historical data obtained from [21] is clustered using unsupervised learning. In this paper, k-Means clustering technique is utilized, and the optimal number of clusters is determined using the elbow method, described in [22]. Using this approach, daily solar radiation curves for the entire year are generated based on CP forecasts with 90% confidence intervals. The number of clusters for each day reflects the variations in historical data while capturing the significant differences within these historical data for the same day in different years, as shown in Figure 3. The probability of each forecasted cluster is proportional to the frequency of occurrence of the clusters in the historical data for the same day. These probabilities are calculated as the ratio of the number of historical solar radiation curves within a cluster to the total number of historical solar radiation curves for that day.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3 Forecasted rooftop PV output for 17.06 with probability of: (a) 72.5%, (b) 22.5% and (c) 5%

To simulate the uncertainties associated with the residential load data, a synthetic load was created. The synthetic load includes both uncontrollable and controllable appliances,

considering that part of the load consumption depends on solar radiation (e.g., lights) and temperature (e.g., fridge, cooling, and heating). Therefore, N-HITS is used to forecast temperature in the same manner as described previously for PV generation. Additionally, a probability is assigned to the usage period of each appliance. This approach generates different load diagrams for each day of the year, while identifying the flexible appliances that can participate in DSM [23, 24].

To determine the optimal BESS capacity for a year, for each day of that year, a random number between 0 and 1 is generated. Based on the value of the random number, and the probabilities of occurrence of each cluster for the solar radiation and temperature (the probabilities of solar radiation CP forecasts on Fig. 3), a cluster is selected. For the selected cluster, a Monte Carlo simulation is performed using the 90% high and low forecast intervals as bounds. The distribution is based on historical data curves within the cluster, maintaining the same probability distribution for the specific day. For each day, 1000 simulations are performed and a random curve is chosen as the solar radiation and the temperature for the specified day, which is depicted on Fig. 4. Then, using the solar radiation curve, the data for the installed rooftop PV system of the consumer, and the pvlib library in Python [25], the PV production for that specific day in that year is calculated, providing the generated power from the rooftop PV plant. Additionally, using the solar radiation, temperature, and synthetic load, a load diagram for the consumer is generated for the same day of the year.

Fig. 4 Monte Carlo simulation of cluster 1 for 17.06.

After obtaining the rooftop PV production and the load diagram of the consumer for each day of the year, the methodology reschedules the appliances through load shifting to minimize imported energy from the network and maximize self-consumption. Subsequently, the BESS is charged and discharged in a manner that minimizes the annual costs for the household, including electricity costs, based on time-of-use (ToU) tariffs, and battery-related costs.

This process is repeated 100 times, representing 100 different years, resulting in 100 optimal BESS capacities—one for each simulated year. As a result, a distribution of the optimal capacities across all simulations is obtained. Finally, the BESS capacity with the highest frequency of occurrence across all simulations is selected as the optimal capacity for

the specific consumer. The schematic representation of the methodology of finding the distribution of optimal BESS capacities is depicted in Fig. 5. The inputs required to determine the optimal BESS capacity are historical solar radiation and temperature data for the consumer's location, appliances usage patterns and ToU tariffs.

Fig. 5 Schematic representation of methodology for obtaining optimal BESS capacity

3. Optimization problem statement and modelling

In this paper a novel two-stage optimization problem is proposed. In the first stage, load shifting technique, as part of DSM strategies, is applied to controllable appliances to reduce the consumer's total daily costs, accounting for the energy generated by the rooftop PV system. In the second stage, the optimal battery capacity is determined as a minimization problem that reduces the consumer's total annual costs after load shifting has been applied. A mathematical model of the grid-connected prosumer with a BESS is developed to be used in the minimization problem. The details about the model and the optimization procedures are described in the following subchapters.

3.1. Load shifting

Load shifting refers to shifting electricity consumption throughout the day without reducing the total amount of electricity consumed. This is achieved by changing the time when the consumer uses an appliance. The consumer is motivated to do so by a stimulus, in this case, a reduction of the daily costs for electricity [26]. To achieve this, the following optimization problem is defined:

$$\min \sum_{a \in A} \left[\max \left[0, \left(L_h^{ncon} + L_{a,h}^{con} - P_h \right) \right] \cdot C_{b,h} - \max \left[0, \left(P_h - L_h^{ncon} - L_{a,h}^{con} \right) \right] \cdot C_{s,h} \right], \forall h \in H \quad (1)$$

where, A is the set of controllable appliances, a represents a specific controllable appliance and H represents the time of use of the given appliance a . L_h^{ncon} represents the power of all of the non-controllable appliances at time h , $L_{a,h}^{con}$ represents the power of appliance a at time

h , while P_h represents the power generated by the rooftop PV system at time h . $C_{b,h}$ and $C_{s,h}$ are the prices at which the electricity is bought from and sold to the grid, respectively.

As mentioned before, each controllable appliance has its predefined load profile L_a^{def} . For example, if an appliance is running for three consecutive hours with power consumption of 1 kW, 1 kW and 1.5 kW, respectively, then its predefined load profile would be $L_{a1}^{def} = [1, 1, 1.5]$.

The optimization problem in this paper is solved using a genetic algorithm, subject to the following constraints:

$$L_{a,h}^{con} = L_a^{def} [h-s] \cdot x_{a,h} \quad \forall h, s \in H_{allowed} \quad (2)$$

where, s is the time at which the appliance a is turned on and $H_{allowed}$ is the time interval during which the controllable appliance is permitted to be turned on, while $L_a^{def} [h-s]$ selects the power of the predefined load diagram of the appliance at hour $h-s$ after started running at time s . $x_{a,h}$ ensures the appliance is only turned on for its load profile duration, and is defined as:

$$x_{a,h} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } h \in [s, s+d] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where d is the length of L_a^{def} .

3.2. BESS Model

To simulate the dynamic behavior of the BESS unit, the battery state of charge (SoC) is taken into account. BESS can be charged from surplus PV power (P_{pv2b}), and cheap off-peak power imported from the grid (P_{g2b}). Discharged power from the BESS can be used for supplying the residential load (P_{b2L}), or if profitable for exporting to the grid (P_{b2g}). The BESS's discrete-time model is:

$$SoC_h = SoC_{h-1} + E_h^c \eta_c - E_h^d / \eta_d \quad (4)$$

where SoC_h is the SoC at time h , SoC_{h-1} is the SoC at time $h-1$, E_h^c is the charging energy at time h , E_h^d is the discharging energy at time h , η_c is the charging efficiency factor and η_d is the discharging efficiency factor. E_h^c and E_h^d are calculated as:

$$E_h^c = (P_{pv2b} + P_{g2b}) \cdot \Delta h \quad (5)$$

$$E_h^d = (P_{b2L} + P_{b2g}) \cdot \Delta h \quad (6)$$

Further, at any moment h , SoC is constrained to a minimum (SoC_{min}) and maximum (SoC_{max}):

$$SoC_{min} < SoC_h < SoC_{max} \quad (7)$$

3.3. Load Model

The consumer should always have its energy needs satisfied. Residential load is supplied by the PV (P_{pv2L}), by the BESS (P_{b2L}) and by the utility grid (P_{g2L}), represented with (8).

$$P_L(h) = P_{pv2L}(h) + P_{b2L}(h) + P_{g2L}(h) \quad (8)$$

To calculate the cost associated with the energy supply of the prosumer, the power imported (P_{imp}) and the power exported (P_{exp}) to the grid need to be calculated:

$$P_{imp}(h) = P_{g2L}(h) + P_{g2b}(h) \quad (9)$$

$$P_{exp}(h) = P_{pv2g}(h) + P_{b2g}(h) \quad (10)$$

The total cost associated with the power supply of the prosumer, which needs to be minimized across the whole year, is defined as:

$$\min C = \sum_{d=1}^{365} \left(\sum_{h=0}^{23} (P_{imp,h}^d \cdot C_{b,h}^d - P_{exp,h}^d \cdot C_{s,h}^d) + \frac{n_c^d}{n_{tot}} \cdot C_{b,cpx} \right) \quad (11)$$

where, n_c^d is the number of full cycles of the battery in a day, n_{tot} is the cycle life of the battery, and $C_{b,cpx}$ are the capital expenditures associated with the battery. The number of full cycles of the battery is calculated as follows:

$$n_c^d = \frac{\sum_{h=0}^{23} E_h^d}{E_{cap}} \quad (12)$$

where, E_{cap} is the battery capacity.

By solving this optimization problem, the optimal BESS capacity for a single year is calculated. Repeating the optimization process 100 times generates a distribution of the optimal BESS capacities, which enables us to determine the optimal capacity of the BESS for the prosumer while accounting for the uncertainties of rooftop PV production and load consumption.

4. Data used and results

To demonstrate the advantages of the methodology presented in this paper, the solar radiation for a consumer located in North Macedonia is forecasted using conformal prediction intervals. The N-HITS model employed in this study consists of 6 hidden layers, each with 512 neurons. The rectified linear unit (ReLU) function was chosen as the activation function, and the mean absolute error (MAE) was used as the loss function. The model was pre-trained on 1 million samples obtained from various locations across North Macedonia. To further enhance forecast accuracy, the model was fine-tuned using historical data from the specified consumer's location.

The forecasted solar radiation for each day, along with the probability of occurrence for each cluster, is fed into a Python script, where a Monte Carlo simulation is performed. Firstly,

a representative cluster is randomly chosen for each day, while considering the probability of its occurrence. Then, the Monte Carlo simulation generates 1000 curves for each chosen cluster. And afterwards, a single curve is randomly selected from the set of simulated curves for each day. In this manner a set of 365 curves is created for each simulated year. Finally, this data is passed to another Python script that uses pvlb and the rooftop PV system specifications, detailed in Table 1, to calculate the generated power from the rooftop PV system.

Table 1. Technical parameters of rooftop PV system

Parameter	Value
Tilt angle	20°
Installed peak power	6 kWp
Efficiency of the system	18%

To simulate the consumer, temperature data is obtained using the N-HiTS model and Monte Carlo simulation using the same procedure as described previously for the solar radiation simulation.

The consumer, as mentioned earlier, is synthetic and consists of appliances with predefined load profiles and probability distributions for the time of use, mimicking a typical Macedonian four-person household, as described in [27]. Additionally, the power consumption and use of the appliances depend on the temperature and solar radiation. In this paper, the synthetic load consists of seven non-controllable appliances (refrigerator, lights, air conditioner, heat pump, oven, TV and kitchen appliances) that can be aggregated and four controllable appliances: washing machine, dish washer, dryer and vacuum cleaner. Their allowed time of use and predefined load profiles are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Allowed time of use and predefined load profile for controllable appliances.

Appliance	Allowed time of use	Predefined load diagram
Washing machine	12 – 20	[1, 1, 0.5]
Dish washer	12 – 20	[1, 1, 0.5]
Dryer	16 – 22	[1.5, 1]
Vacuum cleaner	12 – 16	[1]

Afterwards, the load shifting technique is applied to controllable appliances to minimize the electricity costs. The electricity prices used for solving the optimization problem (1) are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Electricity prices.

Period	Price [eurocent/kWh]
Buying Mon-Sat 7am – 1pm and 3pm-10pm	12

price	Otherwise	7
Selling price	All day	5

Figure 6 shows the load profile of the synthetic load and the power generated by the PV system for a single simulation on the 1st of April, both before and after applying the load shifting technique.

(a)

(b)

Fig 6. Consumer's load profile for 1st of April: (a) Before applying load shifting; (b) After applying load shifting.

After applying the load shifting to each day of one-year simulation and reducing the consumer's costs, the optimal BESS capacity is determined to minimize the consumer's annual costs. The technical parameters used for the BESS are presented in Table 4, with the capital cost of the BESS set at 400 €/kWh.

Table 4. Technical parameters of BESS

Parameter	Value
Cycle life	7016
Charge/discharge efficiency	90%
Lower limit of SoC	10%
Upper limit of SoC	90%

After performing 100 simulations, a distribution of potential BESS capacities that consider the uncertainties discussed is obtained. The results are depicted in Fig 7a, which presents the capacities of batteries ranging from 0 to 6 kWh, with a step of 0.5 kWh. To illustrate the advantages of utilizing load shifting in BESS sizing, Fig 7b represents the distribution of optimal BESS capacities when load shifting is not applied.

(a)

(b)

Fig 7. Distribution of optimal BESS Capacities: (a) with load shifting; (b) without load shifting

The results indicate that the optimal BESS capacity for the given prosumer, taking into account the uncertainties in PV production and load demand, and applying load shifting is approximately 2 kWh. This capacity ensures that the prosumer can maximize self-consumption of generated PV energy while minimizing the import of electricity from the grid and minimizing costs. The standard deviation of the optimal BESS capacity is found to be 0.5 kWh, reflecting the variability introduced by the uncertainties in PV production and load demand. On the other hand, the optimal BESS capacity for the prosumer, when load shifting is not applied, is about 4 kW. Analyzing the two figures, it is evident that load shifting can enhance the profitability of rooftop PV systems by reducing the BESS size, and therefore reducing the capital costs of the BESS.

Furthermore, performing 1000 simulations demonstrates its advantages by selecting the optimal BESS capacity that accounts for benefits over a longer time horizon. In contrast, relying solely on historical data can lead to battery oversizing due to accidental events.

5. Conclusion

The probabilistic forecasting approach used in the presented research, incorporating transfer learning, significantly improved the accuracy of PV generation forecasts. By using a pre-trained N-HiTS model on a large dataset and fine-tuning it with local irradiation data,

high-precision forecasts with 90% confidence intervals are achieved. This method ensures that the generated PV production diagrams are realistic and reflective of the actual conditions, thereby enhancing the reliability of the Monte Carlo simulations.

Furthermore, the synthetic load generation technique used in this study provided a robust representation of residential load profiles. By incorporating both non-controllable and controllable appliances and assigning probabilities to different load diagrams for various days and seasons, a dynamic and realistic load model is created. This model is crucial in capturing the variations in residential load demand and assessing the impact of load shifting strategies.

The load shifting algorithm, based on genetic algorithms, effectively minimizes the import of electricity from the grid by optimizing the operation of non-controllable appliances. By scheduling these appliances during periods of high PV generation or low grid tariffs, the algorithm reduces the overall energy costs for the prosumer. The integration of the optimized load diagram with the BESS operation further enhances the economic benefits, ensuring that the BESS is charged and discharged in an optimal manner. The combination of these methodologies - Monte Carlo simulation, probabilistic forecasting, synthetic load generation, and load shifting optimization - provides a comprehensive framework for determining the optimal BESS capacity for residential prosumers. The analyses presented in the paper show that the BESS capacity is about two times higher without applying a load shifting strategy. The result confirms that the potential economic benefits of BESS can be understated if the prosumers have no opportunities to apply such strategies. Therefore, this approach not only addresses the uncertainties in PV generation and load demand but also offers practical solutions for enhancing the economic feasibility of BESS.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Goran Veljanovski: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Data curation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Pande Popovski:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Validation. **Katerina Bilbiloska:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Petar Krstevski:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Aleksandra Krkoleva Mateska:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Metodija Atanasovski:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process:

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the language and readability of the presented work to a limited extent. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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